

A mathematical model for controlling time around cancer cells by using spinors and EM waves

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Abstract: Up to date, many medical methods have been proposed to prevent of PD1/PD-L1 and other harmful connections between T-cells and tumor ones; however; they are very expensive and some of them don't work very good. In this paper, we suggest a theoretical system which may help us to control time around tumor cells and remove any harmful connection. This system is built from: 1. Two electromagnetic waves with spins 1 and -1 which move in opposite directions respect to each other around the earth. 2. N towers which control motions of electromagnetic waves around the earth 3. N entangled spinning two circles sub-systems. In each sub-system, there are two coupled circles and each circle is built from spinors with opposite spins respect to spins in other circle. To form these circles, near each tower, two electromagnetic waves divide into two types of photons with spins 1 and -1. Then, these photons decay into spinors like electrons with spins $1/2$ and $-1/2$. These spinors move around tower and build two coupled spinning circles. Circles around a tower have opposite spins respect to circles around the near towers and make maximally entanglements with them. These circles, towers and electromagnetic waves form a quantum tunnel. Circles act the role of gates for this quantum tunnel. When a spinor enters to one gate, distributions of spins within a quantum tunnel around the earth change. In these conditions, to return the stable state, system produces the same spinor with opposite spin respect to initial one at the same point. A stationary observer sees that a spinor is eaten by quantum tunnel and immediately, a spinor with opposite spin is emerged. However, a moving observer like a photon sees that a spinor enters to the quantum tunnel, turns over the earth and returns to the initial point with opposite spin and after passing a quantum time towards past. We can use of this property in controlling connections between biological molecules. Each connection like PD1/PD-L1 is formed from pairing spinors with opposite spins. When, these connections are placed near a gate of this quantum tunnel, some spins reverse and for some particles like photons, time returns. Consequently, connections could be broken and molecules become free. This a theoretical model which could be formulated by using the concepts of quantum and general relativity.

Keywords: Tumor; T-cell; PD1/PD-L1; Time; Electromagnetic wave

I. Introduction:

When a tumor emerges, the body's defense and immune system responses and tries to solve the problem. For example, in some diseases, T-cells and some other biological molecules may attack tumor cells. To response, some tumor cells defense from themselves against these cells and by producing some PD1/PD-L1 connections, kill T-cells [1-3]. These connections are emerged by coupling of the programmed death-ligand 1 (PD-L1) with its receptor, programmed cell death protein 1 (PD-1). Up to date, several medical methods and inhibitors have been introduced to

block PD1 and PD-L1. For example, Pembrolizumab, Nivolumab and Cemiplimab act as the inhibitors of PD1[4-6] and Atezolizumab or Durvalumab act as inhibitors of PD-L1 [7,8] . However, some of these inhibitors are very expensive and people in non-developing countries couldn't pay expenses. On the other hand, some of these medical methods don't work and couldn't prevent of harmful connections around tumors of some patients.

In this paper, using the physical concepts, we introduce more cheapest methods for blocking PD1/PD-L1 connections. In this method, we put harmful connections near a quantum tunnel which is produced by two spinning waves with opposite spins and entangled circles of spinors. Within these connections, each electron is coupled to an electron with opposite spin through exchanged photons. Quantum tunnel takes one of electrons and also one of photons. For electron, its spin becomes reverse and returns to connection. This electron has the parallel spin with its spouse in initial pair and their connection could be cancelled. For photon, not only the arrow of its spin changes, but a shift in its time occurs [10-12]. Because, the quantum tunnel acts like the accelerating or non-inertial frame and it has been known that in non-inertial frames , time has a different definition respect to stationary system. Thus, not only PD1 and PD-L1 may be disconnected but they may return to the past.

The outline of paper is as follows: In section II, we describe the model and design a quantum tunnel from spinors and electromagnetic waves. Then, we consider the role of this tunnel in decoupling PD1/PD-L1 connections. In section III, we formulate the model and obtain the changes in time near the quantum tunnel.

II. The model: A quantum tunnel from spinning photons and spinors

Previously, it has been known that a non-inertial frame or accelerating system could act like a black hole system. In a black hole system, we define a Hawking temperature which has a relation with black hole mass. By increasing this temperature, observed time changes and we have to define new definitions for space and time. In parallel, in an accelerating system, we could define a Unruh temperature which depends on the acceleration. By increasing the acceleration and Unruh temperature, observed time changes. We can write:

$$T_{Hawking}, T_{unruh} \rightarrow \text{Change in observed time} \quad (1)$$

Where $T_{Hawking}, T_{unruh}$ are the Hawking and Unruh temperatures and have below relations:

$$T_{Hawking} \rightarrow \frac{1}{GM}$$

(2)

$$T_{unruh} \rightarrow \frac{a}{2\pi}$$

(3)

Where M is the mass and a is the acceleration.

Now, the question arises that could we observe these temperatures on the earth. Suppose that you fly around the earth by an airplane. Your acceleration can be obtained from below equation:

$$a \rightarrow \frac{V^2}{R}$$

(4)

Present machines have very low velocity and consequently, their accelerations are small. Thus, we couldn't observed any change in temperature and time. We have:

$$a_{airplane} \rightarrow \frac{u^2}{R}$$

(5)

$$a_{airplane} \rightarrow 0$$

(6)

$$T_{unruh} \rightarrow 0$$

(7)

$$\textit{Observed time} \rightarrow \textit{classical time}$$

(8)

Above equations show that because of very small velocity of our machines or airplanes, we don't detect Unruh temperature and consequently, we see only classical time (See Figure 1). In fact, for moving and stationary classical objects, the concept of time is the same. Classical objects have low velocities and big sizes.

Above results couldn't be true always. For quantum particles like photons and electrons, the velocity is very big and consequently, acceleration increases. This causes to a significant change

in Unruh temperature. Thus, space-time changes and quantum particles see different time respect to classical objects. We can write:

$$a_{\text{quantum particle}} \rightarrow \frac{C^2}{R}$$

$$T_{\text{unruh}} \gg 0$$

Observed time → *quantum time*

(9)

Above equations show that quantum particles have very large velocities and accelerations and detect the Unruh temperature clearly. This means that space and time have different definitions and moving quantum particles observe different passing of time respect to stationary ones (See Figure 1).

These quantum properties of time may have many applications, specially in biology. However, we should propose a model which describes differences between observed times by different particles. In this model, the role of spin is very important and particles with different spins observe different times. We have several types of spinning particles. Spinors with spin $\frac{1}{2}$ have the below properties (See Figure 2):

1. Spinors with opposite spins attract each other, while parallel spins repel each other.
2. Suppose that arrow of one spin in a pair of anti-parallel spinors change. This causes that spinors go away from each other and try to find the farthest point .
3. If this event occurs on a circle, the farthest point is the initial point and consequently, spins return to their initial place.
4. If the circle be filled by parallel spins, the velocity of transferring increases and tend to infinity. Because parallel spins repel each other. This means that parallel spins turn over the circle and return to initial points immediately and without passing any time.

Spinning particles with spin 1 have the below behaviors (See Figure 3):

5. These spinning particles could decay into two parallel spinors. For example, a photon could decay into two parallel electrons.
6. An electromagnetic wave (EM wave) could be formed from many photons. Consequently, a wave could decay into many spinors.
7. Two electromagnetic waves which their photons have opposite directions could form a tunnel which connects two entangled system. Each system could contain two circles which spins of each of them be in opposite arrow respect to spins of other circle.

8. If a spinor enters into this tunnel from one side, a spinor with opposite spin is induced in other side.

Using properties of electromagnetic waves and spinors, maybe, we could build a system which returns time around quantum particles. In this system (See Figure 4):

9. We use of towers around the earth. Each tower take electromagnetic waves and convert them to one entangled sub-system.
10. A tunnel of waves connect entangled sub-systems.
11. These entangled sub-systems are formed from two circles with opposite spins.
12. Near each two circle sub-system , there is another two circle sub-system with opposite spins.
13. Any spinor which attracted by this system, move along a tunnel and returns to initial point.
14. For spinor itself, this transferring and motion occurs immediately, while for photons which carry this spinor along the circle, a time is passed. This time is different from classical time and may be towards future or reversely towards past depending on initial conditions.

By using this system, we can control time around biological cells. Specially, we may control interactions between T-cells and tumors and prevent of PD1/PD-L1 connections. To this aim (See Figure 5),

15. We put an end of spinning tunnel in this system near a PD1/PD-L1 connection.
16. Each connect is built from pairing spinors with opposite spins. These spinors are attracted by system, turn over a circle and return to their initial place with opposite spin.
17. Two events occur:
 - A: Two anti-parallel spins convert to parallel spins and connections are broken.
 - B: System acts like a time tunnel and by returning time, two molecules become separated.

Fig 1: A compare between acceleration and observed times by classical and quantum objects.

Figure 2: Parallel spins turn over a circle and return to their initial points.

Figure 3: A tunnel of two electromagnetic waves connects two entangled systems. These systems are formed from two circles with opposite spins.

Figure 4. A system around the earth which is formed from towers, a tunnel of electromagnetic waves and some sub-entangled spinning circles. Each spinor which is absorbed by this tunnel returns to its initial place without passing time, while photons see a passing of quantum time.

Figure 5. A system including entangled spinning circles, towers and a tunnel of electromagnetic waves may control time around tumor cells and prevent of PD1/PD-L1 connections.

III. Mathematical Results:

In previous section, we have described the model and shown that by a system including waves and spinors, we may control time around biological cells. In this system, we formulate the model. To begin discussion, we remember the below accelerating force for a particle which moves around a circle:

$$a = \frac{v^2}{R}$$

$$F = M_p \frac{V^2}{R}$$

(10)

Above acceleration may produce the below energy:

$$U = -M_p V^2 \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right) \quad (11)$$

Where M_p is the particle mass, V is the velocity, R is the radius of (earth + tower) and R_0 is the radius of earth. Previously, it has been known that each photon package has the below energy:

$$E = M_p V^2 = M_p C^2 = h\nu \quad (12)$$

Where h is the plank constant and ν is the frequency of photon. Substituting equation (12) in equation (11) gives:

$$U = -h\nu \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right) \quad (13)$$

Above energy depends on the frequency of photons, radius of earth and radius of (earth + tower) or radius of electromagnetic wave circles. This energy changes the space time and produce the below time for stationary photon:

$$t'_{\text{photon}} = \frac{t_{\text{photon}}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2U}{C^2}}} = \frac{t_{\text{photon}}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2h\nu \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)}{C^2}}} \quad (14)$$

Where t'_{photon} is the life time of stationary photon and t_{photon} is the life time of moving photon. It is clear that moving photons see different times respect to stationary photons. We can write:

$$\Delta t_{\text{photon}} = t'_{\text{photon}} - t_{\text{photon}} = \frac{t_{\text{photon}}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2h\nu \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)}{C^2}}} - t_{\text{photon}} \quad (15)$$

This difference between observed times by moving and stationary photons depends on the frequency of photons, radius of earth and height of towers or wave cycles. The same relations could be written for other high speed particles like spinors with spin $\frac{1}{2}$. We can write:

$$t'_{electron} = \frac{t_{electron}}{\sqrt{1-\frac{2U}{C^2}}} = \frac{t_{electron}}{\sqrt{1-\frac{2M_e V^2 \text{Ln}\left(\frac{R_0}{R}\right)}{C^2}}} \rightarrow$$

$$\rightarrow \Delta t_{electron} = t'_{electron} - t_{electron} = \frac{t_{electron}}{\sqrt{1-\frac{2M_e V^2 \text{Ln}\left(\frac{R_0}{R}\right)}{C^2}}} - t_{electron}$$
(16)

Where $t'_{electron}$ is the life time of stationary electron, $t_{electron}$ is the life time of moving electron, M_e is the mass of electrons, V is the velocity of electron and C is the velocity of light. By increasing the speed or velocity of electrons, observed times by moving and stationary particles become different.

Totally, for spinning particles like photons and electrons which move within a system like that in figures 4 and 5 or around a circle, we have two observed times:

$$\Delta t_{spin,pair} = t'_{spin,pair} - t_{spin,pair} = \begin{cases} 0 - t_{spin} & \text{for } V = \text{Infinity} \\ \frac{t_{spin}}{\sqrt{1-\frac{2M_{spin} V^2 \text{Ln}\left(\frac{R_0}{R}\right)}{C^2}}} - t_{spin} & \text{for } V = v \end{cases}$$
(17)

Above times depend on the spin of particles and their velocities. For spinors with spin $\frac{1}{2}$, transferring of states occur immediately ($V = \text{Infinity}$), while transferring of mass has a limited velocity ($V = v$). Thus, these particles could experience two types of times. However, if a circle be filled by parallel spins, both transferring of states and masses occur immediately (See Figures 3 and 4). Because, parallel spins repel each other and spins move around the circles very fast. For photons, however, we have the velocity of light at most and thus, these particles see only one type of quantum time.

We can make a connection between observed time by photons and electrons especially in systems like figures 4 and 5. In this system, near a tower, some photons convert to two spinors:

$$Photon (\uparrow\uparrow) \rightarrow \uparrow + \uparrow$$

$$Photon (\downarrow\downarrow) \rightarrow \downarrow + \downarrow$$

(18)

This is because that each photon has a spin 1 and can convert into two spinors with spin $\frac{1}{2}$. Arrows of spinors should be parallel. We can write the below relation between energies:

$$E_{Photon (\uparrow\uparrow)} = 2E_{Electron (\uparrow)} \rightarrow h\nu = 2 m_e C^2$$

(19)

Where $E_{Photon (\uparrow\uparrow)}$ is the energy of a photon and $E_{Electron (\uparrow)}$ is the energy of an electron. Above equation shows that each photon can decay into two parallel spins. On the other hand, each wave is built from n photons. Thus, a wave could decay into 2n electrons. We can write the below relation between their energies:

$$E_{Wave(2n\uparrow)} = nE_{Photon (\uparrow\uparrow)} = 2nE_{Electron (\uparrow)}$$

(20)

Where $E_{Wave(2n\uparrow)}$ is the energy of an electromagnetic wave with a special spin. Near a tower, we have more spinning waves. Thus, for two waves with opposite spins, we can write:

$$E_{2Wave,tower(2n\uparrow\downarrow)} = n[E_{Photon (\uparrow\uparrow)} + E_{Photon (\downarrow\downarrow)}] = 2n[E_{Electron (\uparrow)} + E_{Electron (\downarrow)}]$$

(21)

Where $E_{2Wave,tower(2n\uparrow\downarrow)}$ is the energy of waves around a tower. These waves could form a subsystem of two anti-parallel spinning circles (See Figures 4 and 5). Above equation isn't complete and ignore differences between photonic energies. We can rewrite it as below:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{2Wave,tower(2n\uparrow\downarrow,j)} &= \sum_{i=1}^n [E_{Photon (\uparrow,i,j)} + E_{Photon (\downarrow,i,j)}] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{2n} [E_{Electron (\uparrow,i,j)} + E_{Electron (\downarrow,i,j)}] \end{aligned}$$

(22)

Where index j denotes the jth tower. These energies cause to a change in space-time coordinates. To obtain amount of these charges, we should calculate for decaying photons to electrons. A quantum state of an electron near a tower could be written in terms of sub-states :

$$|e, \uparrow, ij\rangle = \cos(\alpha_{ij})|0, ij\rangle + \sin(\alpha_{ij})|\uparrow, ij\rangle$$

$$\tan(\alpha_{ij,\uparrow}) = e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\uparrow,ij)}{T_{ij}}}$$

(23)

Where $|e, \uparrow, ij\rangle$ is the state of an electron with spin $\frac{1}{2}$, j is the index related to tower, I is the index related to ith electron around that tower and $E_{Electron}(\uparrow,ij)$ is the energy of this electron. Also, T_{ij} is temperature in point of I around tower j in figure 4, $|0, ij\rangle$ is the ground state of non-existed electron without decay and $|\uparrow, ij\rangle$ is the excited state of existed electron related to decay of a photon into electrons. The probability for the emergence of this electron is:

$$P_{ij,\uparrow} = \frac{e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\uparrow,ij)}{T_{ij}}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{Electron}(\uparrow,ij)}{T_{ij}}}}}$$

(24)

This probability depends on the energy of electrons. High energetic electrons will be emerged by lower probability. Totally, energies of waves around a tower can be obtained in terms of energies of electrons:

$$E_{2Wave,tower(2n\uparrow\downarrow,j)} = \sum_{i=1}^{2n} [P_{ij,\uparrow} E_{Electron}(\uparrow,ij) + P_{ij,\downarrow} E_{Electron}(\downarrow,ij)]$$

(25)

Substituting probability of (24) in equation (25) gives:

$$E_{2Wave,tower(2n\uparrow\downarrow,j)} = \sum_{i=1}^{2n} \left[\frac{e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\uparrow,ij)}{T_{ij}}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{Electron}(\uparrow,ij)}{T_{ij}}}}} E_{Electron}(\uparrow,ij) + \frac{e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\downarrow,ij)}{T_{ij}}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{Electron}(\downarrow,ij)}{T_{ij}}}}} E_{Electron}(\downarrow,ij) \right]$$

(26)

Above energy is related to a tower only. However, for all towers in figures 4 and 5, we obtain the below equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{2Wave \text{ around circle}} &= \sum_{j=1}^N E_{2Wave, tower(2n \uparrow \downarrow, j)} \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^{2n} \left[\frac{e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\uparrow, ij)}}{T_{ij}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{Electron}(\uparrow, ij)}{T_{ij}}}}} E_{Electron}(\uparrow, ij) + \frac{e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\downarrow, ij)}}{T_{ij}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{Electron}(\downarrow, ij)}{T_{ij}}}}} E_{Electron}(\downarrow, ij) \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

Above equation shows that total energy of towers in figures 4 and 5 depend on the temperatures and energies of electrons around towers. This energy changes space-time coordinates and produce below observed time:

$$\begin{aligned}
 t'_{2Wave \text{ around circle}} &= \sum_{j=1}^N t'_{2Wave, tower(2n \uparrow \downarrow, j)} \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^{2n} \left[\frac{e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\uparrow, ij)}}{T_{ij}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{Electron}(\uparrow, ij)}{T_{ij}}}}} t'_{Electron}(\uparrow, ij) + \frac{e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\downarrow, ij)}}{T_{ij}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{Electron}(\downarrow, ij)}{T_{ij}}}}} t'_{Electron}(\downarrow, ij) \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

Where $t'_{Electron}(\downarrow, ij)$ is the stationary time of an electron with below relation:

$$t'_{Electron}(\downarrow, ij) = \frac{t_{Electron}(\downarrow, ij)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_{Electron}(\downarrow, ij) [V_{Electron}(\downarrow, ij)]^2 \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)}{C^2}}} \tag{29}$$

Above time depends on the velocity of electron, velocity of light, electronic mass and radius of circles.

Now, suppose that an electron becomes closed to a circle at one end of wave tunnels in figures 4 and 5. The needed time that this spinor be transmitted along tunnel and returns to its initial point could be obtained from below relation:

$$\begin{aligned}
t_{spinor \text{ around circle}} &= \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\uparrow,j)}{T_j}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{Electron}(\uparrow,j)}{T_j}}}} t'_{2Wave,tower(2n\uparrow,j)} \\
&= \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\uparrow,j)}{T_j}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{Electron}(\uparrow,j)}{T_j}}}} \\
\otimes \sum_{i=1}^{2n} &\left[\frac{e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\uparrow,i)}{T_{ij}}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{Electron}(\uparrow,i)}{T_{ij}}}}} \frac{t_{Electron}(\uparrow,i)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_{Electron}(\uparrow,i) [V_{Electron}(\uparrow,i)]^2 \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)}}{C^2}} \right. \\
&+ \left. \frac{e^{\frac{-E_{Electron}(\downarrow,i)}{T_{ij}}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{Electron}(\downarrow,i)}{T_{ij}}}}} \frac{t_{Electron}(\downarrow,i)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_{Electron}(\downarrow,i) [V_{Electron}(\downarrow,i)]^2 \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)}}{C^2}} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Where T_j is temperature at tower j , T_{ij} is temperature at point I around tower j and $E_{Electron}(\downarrow,i)$ is the energy of electron I around tower j . This spinor moves around the circle and return to initial point. For spin, itself, passed time is zero ($t'_{spinor \text{ around circle}}$). However, photons which carry this spinor see a quantum time ($t_{spinor \text{ around circle}}$). We can write:

$$\Delta t_{spinor \text{ around circle}} = t'_{spinor \text{ around circle}} - t_{spinor \text{ around circle}}$$

$$t'_{spinor \text{ around circle}} = 0$$

$$\Delta t_{spinor \text{ around circle}} = 0 - t_{spinor \text{ around circle}}$$

$$\Delta t_{Electron \text{ around circle}} = -t_{spinor \text{ around circle}}$$

(31)

Above equation shows that when an electron enters into a tunnel like the one in figure 4, a difference between observed times occur. Maybe, we can claim that for quantum particles, a time loop is emerged or even time may be returned.

We can use of this property for disconnecting harmful connections between tumor cells and T-cells like PD1/PD-L1 ones. We now that a connection between molecules is emerged by pairing M electrons with opposite spins. Thus, we can write:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta t_{PD1-PD-L1} &= \sum_{k=1}^M \Delta t_{\text{Electron around circle},k} + \sum_{l=1}^L \Delta t_{\text{Electron around circle},l} \\
\rightarrow \Delta t_{PD1-PD-L1} &= - \sum_{k=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^{2n} \left[\frac{e^{\frac{-E_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,ijk)}}{T_{ijk}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,ijk)}}{T_{ijk}}}} \frac{t_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,ijk)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,ijk) [V_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,ijk)]^2 \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)}{C^2}}} \right. \\
&\quad + \left. \frac{e^{\frac{-E_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,ijk)}}{T_{ijk}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,ijk)}}{T_{ijk}}}} \frac{t_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,ijk)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,ijk) [V_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,ijk)]^2 \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)}{C^2}}} \right] \\
&\quad \otimes \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{e^{\frac{-E_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,jk)}}{T_{jk}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-E_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,jk)}}{T_{jk}}}} \\
&= - \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^{2n} \left[\frac{e^{\frac{-E_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,ijl)}}{T_{ijl}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,ijl)}}{T_{ijl}}}} \frac{t_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,ijl)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,ijl) [V_{\text{Electron}}(\uparrow,ijl)]^2 \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)}{C^2}}} \right. \\
&\quad + \left. \frac{e^{\frac{-E_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,ijl)}}{T_{ijl}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-2E_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,ijl)}}{T_{ijl}}}} \frac{t_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,ijl)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,ijl) [V_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,ijl)]^2 \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)}{C^2}}} \right] \\
&\quad \otimes \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{e^{\frac{-E_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,jl)}}{T_{jl}}}{\sqrt{1 + e^{\frac{-E_{\text{Electron}}(\downarrow,jl)}}{T_{jl}}}}
\end{aligned}$$

Above equation shows that near a quantum tunnel like the big circles in figure 5, some of electrons in PD1/PD-L1 connections may be attracted and turn over the circles. When, these particles return to their initial places, their spins reverse and consequently, initial pairs are broken. Also, times for quantum particles change and system goes to past and connections between molecules disappear. This paradox may be used in curing cancers.

Conclusion:

In this research, we have proposed a model to return time in biological systems, reverse spins and break harmful PD1/PD-L1 connections between tumor and T-cells. In this model, we have designed a system from electromagnetic waves, towers and spinors. Electromagnetic waves have spins 1 and -1 and form a wave tunnel around the earth. Towers take electromagnetic waves and divide them into photons. Each photon with spin 1 could decay into two spinors like two electrons with spin $\frac{1}{2}$. There are two types of spinors with spins $\frac{1}{2}$ and $-\frac{1}{2}$. Spinors with spin $\frac{1}{2}$ form a circle which is coupled to a circle from spinors with spin $-\frac{1}{2}$. Two coupled circles around each tower are entangled with near coupled circles with opposite spins. Entangled circles act like gates for a quantum tunnel. When an electron is entered into a gate, distributions of spins along the tunnel change and system gives a spinor with opposite spin. An stationary electron sees that this event occurs immediately, while a moving photon sees that electron is passed the tunnel after a period of time. This change in time may be negative and consequently, for photons, time could be returned. A connection like PD1/PD-L1 is formed from spinors like electrons and spins like photons. When this connection becomes close to a gate, spins of some spinors reverse and time for photons is returned and consequently, connection is broken. We have formulated the model and obtained the amount of changes in time in terms of velocity of electrons and photons and number of towers.

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